

A Study on Prevalence and Risk Factors of Hypertension among Junior Resident Doctors of Medical College Hospital, Telangana

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the number one cause of death globally. Doctors' health is critical because they must be healthy to perform their jobs optimally under challenging work environments. They are known to have a lifestyle that can make them highly vulnerable to CVD. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of hypertension and obesity among doctors in a medical college hospital in Telangana, India. **Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted for two months among Junior resident doctors of a government medical college in Telangana. After informed consent, participants completed a semi-structured questionnaire followed by anthropometry and three seated blood-pressure readings, and data were entered in Excel and analyzed using SPSS software. **Results:** 100 resident doctors participated in the study, 53 females (53%) and 47 males (47%). The mean age of the study population was 26.8 ± 2.4 years. The prevalence of hypertension was 9%, and 33 participants (33%) had prehypertension. The 95% Confidence Interval (CI) for hypertension prevalence was 4.2% to 16.2%. **Conclusion:** Despite medical knowledge, excess weight and central obesity were common. Workplace wellness programs emphasizing a healthy diet, regular physical activity, and periodic BP monitoring are recommended.

Keywords: Hypertension, Prehypertension, Junior doctors, Prevalence, risk factors.

INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension is a chronic lifestyle disease and an important public health problem worldwide. A recent report indicates that nearly one billion adults had hypertension in 2000, and this is predicted to increase to 1.56 billion by 2025 (1).

Knowledge and awareness regarding CVDs and the associated risk factors are expected to be good among doctors since they have access to information. Non-communicable diseases are a significant health concern for doctors, just as they are for the general population. However, they are also known to have a sedentary lifestyle with high levels of stress, lack of proper rest, and irregular eating habits, making them highly vulnerable to cardiovascular diseases (2,3).

Doctors, like many professionals, may experience high levels of stress, unhealthy dietary habits due to the hectic nature of their work. The high-pressure environment of health care can lead to significantly increased stress levels. Prolonged sitting or standing with long hours of work in turn contribute to a sedentary lifestyle, obesity. While doctors are trained in infection control and management, they still face a

very high risk of exposure to infectious diseases, which complicate the underlying NCDs. Reduced productivity, increased health care costs, and reduced quality of life are the impacts of NCDs on doctors. Prevention and management include a supportive and stress-free environment, wellness programs, early detection, and screening.

JNC 8 defined pre-hypertension as systolic blood pressure of 120-139mm of Hg and diastolic of 80-89mm of Hg in persons with 18years of age. Pre-hypertensives are at increased risk of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. The prevalence of hypertension has increased globally as a result of aging populations and rising rates of obesity and overweight. Multiple studies are looking at the prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors in the general population, but only a few studies are looking at the cardiovascular risk factors among doctors in India (4,5). This study aims to determine the prevalence and associated factors of hypertension among resident doctors of the tertiary care Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Hospital, Warangal.

Objectives:

- 1) To estimate the prevalence of hypertension among junior residents
- 2) To determine the risk factors associated with hypertension among junior residents

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Duration: This was a cross-sectional study done in April and May 2025.

Study Population: Junior residents in Kakatiya Medical College, Warangal.

Inclusion Criteria: Junior residents working at the medical college hospital in Warangal, who are willing to give consent.

Exclusion Criteria: Junior residents who joined within one year of the start of data collection were excluded from the study.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique: The required sample size was determined using the formula Z^2PQ/d^2 , assuming a prevalence rate of 29.4%, a precision of 10%, and a 95% confidence interval. The calculated sample size was 100. Out of 544 junior residents, 100 junior residents were selected by simple random sampling. List of junior residents was obtained from college academic section and a new list was made excluding the junior residents who joined within one year of the start of data collection, which was the sampling frame and 100 junior residents were selected using simple random sampling.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were gathered using a semi-structured questionnaire administered through face-to-face interviews. Prior informed consent was obtained from all participants. The collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics were used for summarizing data, while chi-square tests were employed to assess associations between hypertension and sociodemographic, risk factors factors.

RESULTS:

Out of 100 participants, 53 were females (53%) and 47 were males (47%). The mean age of the study population was 26.8 ± 2.4 years.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the distribution of male and female doctors.

Figure 2: Distribution of participants according to year of study

The distribution of participants by year of study was as follows: JR-1 – 6 (6%), JR-2 – 28 (28%), JR-3 – 66 (66%)
 The mean height of the participants was 164.88 ± 9.3 cm, while the mean weight was 63.3 ± 12.9 kg. The mean Body Mass Index (BMI) was 23.3 ± 4.1 kg/m². The mean waist-hip ratio (WHR) was 0.94 ± 0.09 . Mean systolic blood pressure was 116.42 ± 9.4 mm of Hg, and the mean diastolic blood pressure was found to be 77 ± 6.8 mm of Hg. Regarding blood pressure status, 8 participants (8%) were found to have hypertension (defined as SBP ≥ 140 mmHg and/or DBP ≥ 90 mmHg), while 44 participants (44%) had prehypertension (SBP 120–139 mmHg or DBP 80–89 mmHg without meeting criteria for hypertension). The 95% Confidence Interval (CI) for hypertension prevalence was 2.58% to 13.42% (8 ± 5.42)

Table 1: Depicting the frequency of risk factors/associates for hypertension(n=100)

Risk factors		Frequency/percentage
Tobacco	Current	3
	Ex	4
	Never	93
Alcohol	Light	16
	Moderate	5
	Ex	3
	Never	76
Addition of extra salt to food		66
Intake of processed food		91
Vigorous physical activity		25
Moderate physical activity		61
Family history of hypertension		44
Symptoms of hypertension		9

Table 2: chi-square, p-values of independent variables

Variable	X ² value	P value
age	13.38	0.2
Gender	4.74	0.09
Religion	1.53	0.8
Marital status	3.88	0.4
Tobacco	10.6	0.03*
Alcohol	5.75	0.4
Diet	7.37	0.2
Addition of Extra salt in food	1.78	0.7
Intake of processed food	8.44	0.2
Moderate physical activity	1.68	0.4
Vigorous physical activity	0.72	0.6
BMI	8.3	0.2
WHR	4.7	0.09
Family history	10.2	0.03*

DISCUSSION:

Among the resident doctors who participated in this study, females were more represented compared to male participants.

The prevalence of smoking in this study is 3%, which is on the lower side, and Sharma et al reported it as 12.5%. There was no significance in the distribution of height, weight, and body mass index, waist-hip ratio, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, dietary habits, and physical activity. Tobacco consumption, family history of hypertension were found to be statistically significant with a p value <0.05. Smoking was associated with elevated blood pressure seen from our study, and many epidemiological studies from different parts of the globe also reported the same. Intake of extra salt has been considered a positive risk factor, and we found that in 66% of the participants.

The prevalence of hypertension was found to be 8%, while 44% were found to be pre-hypertensive according to the Joint National Committee 8 guidelines. Sharma et al reported that the prevalence of hypertension was 20.7%, which is contrary to this study,⁶. Fanghanel et al reported that the prevalence of hypertension was 22.7% among health care workers⁷. The prevalence of hypertension was reported as 21.6% in a study by Shailendra et al⁸. The prevalence of hypertension was found to be 13% in a study done by Das et al in Bengal⁵, which is almost similar to the current study. In a study done by Mandal in West Bengal reported the prevalence of hypertension was reported as 19.8%¹⁰. Similar to the study by al-Jarky (7%) in Kuwait¹¹, Todkar in Maharashtra (7.24%)¹², Mahmood in Uttar Pradesh (10.81%)¹³.

Although the prevalence of hypertension was comparatively low when compared to older age groups, it is important to detect pre-hypertensives and risk factors to prevent further morbidities and limit the organ damage.

In the present study, the prevalence of overweight and obesity was 15% and 36%, respectively, and the prevalence of central obesity among males was found to be 63.8% and 71.6% among females. In the study by

Shailendra et al,⁸ the prevalence of overweight and obesity was found to be 24.8% and 9.2%, respectively. Also, the prevalence of central obesity among males was found to be 97.5% while that among females was found to be 93%. Gupta et al⁹ prevalence of obesity to be 48.6% among males and 51.4% among females. They also reported that in their study, the prevalence of truncal obesity was 72.4% among males and 65.7% among females. Sharma et al⁸ found the prevalence of overweight and obesity to be 77.3% and that of central obesity to be 80.1% among males and 80.7% among females. This high prevalence of obesity and central obesity among highly educated people might be due to a lack of time and improper food habits, and intake of junk and processed foods.

In the present study, the prevalence of hypertension was higher in males, which was consistent with some studies^{11,14} but dissimilar to some studies¹⁰ where there was no significant relationship^{15,16}. In this study, we observed that BMI had no direct relationship with hypertension, and no statistical significance was seen. This finding is contrary to many other studies.

Strengths and Limitations:

Strengths: Use of a probable sampling technique that ensured adequate representation of the study population. Data collection using a structured questionnaire ensured consistency and comprehensiveness.

Limitations: The study's limitations include its confinement to a single tertiary level hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Self-reported data may have introduced recall bias. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between variables.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of hypertension was 8%, and pre-hypertension was 44%. The prevalence of overweight

was 15%, and obesity was 36%. The prevalence of risk factors for hypertension/ cardiovascular diseases, like the consumption of tobacco, was 3%, and alcohol consumption was 21%. 14% of the subjects do not follow any kind of physical activity.

Recommendations:

Routine health screenings, healthy diet and nutrition, regular physical activity, stress management, wellness programs for doctors and other health care staff, supportive work environment, counselling, and mental health services.

Permissions: Approval obtained from Institutional Ethical Committee.

Source(s) of support: nil

Conflicting Interest: nil

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